

Bessel collocation method for solving variable order fractional problems

Haniye Dehestani¹, Yadollah Ordokhani

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

In this paper, we examined a wide class of the variable order fractional problems such as linear and nonlinear fractional variable order differential equations, variable order fractional functional boundary value problems, variable order fractional pantograph differential equations. The proposed method is a collocation method based on the Bessel polynomials and the operational matrix of derivatives, which transformed equations into a system of non-linear algebraic equations to achieve the approximate solution. By using Caputo fractional derivative, the operational matrix of the variable-order fractional derivatives is constructed. The error analysis shows that the method is convergent. Several numerical results confirm the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Bessel collocation method, Variable-order fractional operational matrix, Variable order fractional differential equations, Variable order fractional functional boundary value problems, Variable order fractional pantograph equations.

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1 Introduction

Recently, several papers have been devoted to the study of variable order fractional problems. Variable fractional problems which have different applications in various areas of science and engineering such as processing of geographical data using variable-order derivatives [14], signature verification [33], constitutive laws in viscoelastic continuum mechanics [22]. Therefore, various numerical and analytical methods developed by many researchers for obtaining the solutions of the variable order fractional differential equations, boundary value problems, delay differential equations. Razminia et al. [24], investigated existence of solution for non-autonomous variable-order fractional differential equations. Sun and Chen [26, 27, 7, 28, 15], introduced some important applications of variable fractional derivative. Liu, Shen and Zhang [19, 8, 9, 25, 10], have been used numerical methods for variable fractional partial differential equations. Yu and Erturk [34] applied a finite difference method to variable order fractional integro-differential equations. Bhrawy and Zaky [3, 4], have been solved variable-order fractional partial differential equations and differential equations. Authors in [13] have solved nonlinear variable order fractional differential equations with Legendre wavelets. Li and Wu [17] reproduced kernel method for variable order fractional boundary value problems. Cao and Qiu [5] introduced a high order numerical scheme for variable order fractional ordinary differential equations. Sweilam et al. [29] have been solved variable order fractional nonlinear delay differential equations.

In this paper, by means of the Bessel collocation method and operational matrix of the variable order fractional derivatives used for solving a wide class of variable order fractional problems. Authors have been used Bessel collocation methods for solving many problems such as Yuzbasi et al. [35] have solved linear neutral delay differential equations with variable coefficients, Yuzbasi and Sezer [36], investigated a class of Lane-Emden type equations, Yuzbasi et al. [37] have worked on pantograph equations, Tohidi et al. [32] have employed Bessel collocation method for solving fractional optimal control problems.

¹speaker

1.1 Applications

Variable-order fractional derivatives have a lot of application in various branches of physics and engineering. So, we describe some models with variable-order fractional derivatives as:

- Tuberculosis is the potentially fatal disease, which resistant to treatment and has been grown in the worldwide. TB models considered in several papers such as [1, 6], which these models incorporate three strains: drug sensitive, multi-drug resistant and extensively drug-resistant. Recently, Sweilam et al. in [30] considered TB model of variable-order fractional derivatives, which includes several factors of spreading TB such as the first infection, the exogenous reinfection and secondary infection along with the resistance factor. Variable-order fractional TB model is a general model than the integer and fractional order models, which can be employed to depict the variable memory of systems.
- In processing and transmitting information in the brain through cortical neurons, bursting and spiking oscillations play important roles. In [31], researchers presented the fractional-order Izhikevich model and analyzed different kinds of oscillations that emerge from the fractional dynamics. The model produced a wide range of neuronal spike responses, including regular spiking, fast spiking, intrinsic bursting, mixed mode oscillations, regular bursting and chattering, by adjusting only the fractional order. Fractional-order Izhikevich model can produce abundant bursting and spiking patterns controlled by the fractional order. when chosen much smaller values of the fractional order the model illustrates fast-spiking.

1.2 Outline of this paper

The outline of this paper is as follows. In Section 2, we introduce some necessary preliminaries and notations of variable order fractional derivatives. In Sections 3 and 4, after describing the basic formulation of Bessel polynomials, we derive the Bessel polynomials operational matrix of integer-order and variable-order fractional derivative. Section 5, we develop a collocation approach to solve the variable-order fractional problems. In Section 6, the error analysis is given. Section 7, we examine our method over a set of variable order fractional linear, non-linear differential equations, variable order fractional functional boundary value problems and variable order fractional pantograph differential equations and compare the results with the results of other methods. Concluding remarks are given in Section 8.

2 Preliminaries and notations

We express some basic definitions and properties of the fractional calculus theory, which are applied further in this paper [11].

Definition 2.1. The fractional derivative of $u(t)$ in the Caputo sense is defined as

$${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}u(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m - \gamma(t))} \int_0^t (t-x)^{m-\gamma(t)-1} u^{(m)}(x) dx, \quad m-1 < \gamma(t) \leq m, \quad m \in \mathbb{N}, \quad t > 0.$$

Based on the above definition, the following results are obtained:

- ${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}C = 0$, (C is a constant.)
- $0 < \gamma(t) \leq 1$, ${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}t^\beta = \begin{cases} 0, & \beta = 0, \\ \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\gamma(t))} t^{\beta-\gamma(t)}, & \beta = 1, 2, \dots \end{cases}$
- $1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2$, ${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}t^\beta = \begin{cases} 0, & \beta = 0, 1, \\ \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\gamma(t))} t^{\beta-\gamma(t)}, & \beta = 2, 3, \dots \end{cases}$

3 Bessel functions

Bessel functions are named for Friedrich Wilhelm Bessel (1784 - 1846). However, Daniel Bernoulli is generally credited with being the first to introduce the concept of Bessel functions in 1732. That, a special case of Sturm-Liouville problem is Bessel equation, as [16, 2]

$$t^2 y''(t) + ty'(t) + (t^2 - n^2)y(t) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where the solution to Bessel's equation yields Bessel functions of the first and second kind as follows:

$$y = A\tilde{J}_n(t) + BY_n(t), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

where A and B are arbitrary constants. $\tilde{J}_n(t)$ in the solution to Bessel's equation is referred to as a Bessel function of the first kind, so that

$$\tilde{J}_n(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!\Gamma(n+k+1)} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right)^{2k+n}, \quad (2)$$

$\Gamma(\lambda)$ is the gamma function. The Bessel functions of the first kind are orthogonal with respect to the weight function $w(t) = t$ in the interval $[0, 1]$ with the orthogonality property

$$\int_0^1 t \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) \tilde{J}_n(\mu t) dt = \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(\lambda)]^2 \delta_{\lambda\mu}, \quad (3)$$

if in the relation λ, μ are roots of the equation $\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) = 0$, where $\delta_{\lambda\mu}$ is the Kronecker function. The n -th degree truncated Bessel functions of first kind are define by [32]

$$J_n(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!\Gamma(k+n+1)} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right)^{2k+n}, \quad 0 \leq t < \infty, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (4)$$

where N is chosen the positive integer so that $N \geq n$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. We can transform the Bessel polynomials of first kind to in N -th degree Taylor polynomials. In matrix form as [37]

$$J(t) = PT(t), \quad (5)$$

where P is defined in [37] and

$$J(t) = [J_0(t), J_1(t), \dots, J_N(t)]^T, \quad T(t) = [T_0(t), T_1(t), \dots, T_N(t)]^T.$$

4 Operational matrices of derivative

The main purpose of this section is to calculate operational matrices of integer and variable order, about fractional derivative of Bessel polynomials.

4.1 Operational matrix of integer-order derivatives

By using the Eq. (4), we obtain operational matrix of integer-order derivatives of Bessel polynomials as

$$\begin{aligned} D^m J(t) &= D^m \left(\sum_{k=0}^s \frac{(-1)^k}{k!\Gamma(k+n+1)} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right)^{2k+n} \right), \quad s = \left\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \right\rfloor, \quad (6) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^s \frac{(-1)^k}{k!\Gamma(k+n+1)} \frac{D^m (t^{2k+n})}{2^{2k+n}} \\ &= \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{m-n}{2} \rfloor}^s \frac{(-1)^k}{k!\Gamma(k+n+1)} \frac{(2k+n)!}{2^{2k+n}(2k+n-m)!} t^{2k+n-m} \\ &= \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{m-n}{2} \rfloor}^s b_{n,k}^m t^{2k+n-m}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$b_{n,k}^m = \frac{(-1)^k}{k! \Gamma(k+n+1)} \frac{(2k+n)!}{2^{2k+n} (2k+n-m)!}.$$

Assume t^{2k+n-m} be expanded by Bessel polynomials as:

$$t^{2k+n-m} = \sum_{j=0}^N c_{k,j}^m J_j(t), \tag{7}$$

substituting Eq. (7) into Eq. (6) for $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} D^m J(t) &= \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-n}{2} \rceil}^s b_{n,k}^m \left(\sum_{j=0}^N c_{k,j}^m J_j(t) \right) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^N \left(\sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-n}{2} \rceil}^s q_{n,k,j}^m \right) J_j(t), \quad q_{n,k,j}^m = b_{n,k}^m c_{k,j}^m, \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^N Q_{n,k,j}^m J_j(t). \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Therefore, we have

$$D^m J(t) = Q_m J(t) = \left[\sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-n}{2} \rceil}^s q_{n,k,0}^m, \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-n}{2} \rceil}^s q_{n,k,1}^m, \dots, \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-n}{2} \rceil}^s q_{n,k,N}^m \right] J(t), \tag{9}$$

where Q_m is called operational matrix of integer-order derivatives of Bessel polynomials.

4.2 Operational matrix of variable-order fractional derivatives

To obtain the operational matrix of variable order fractional derivative of Bessel polynomials, we used Taylor polynomials. The operational matrix of Caputo variable order fractional derivatives of order $0 < \gamma(t) \leq 1$ for the Taylor polynomials, can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} D^{\gamma(t)} T(t) &= D^{\gamma(t)} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ t \\ t^2 \\ \vdots \\ t^N \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))} t^{1-\gamma(t)} \\ \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} t^{2-\gamma(t)} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\gamma(t))} t^{N-\gamma(t)} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= t^{1-\gamma(t)} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))} & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\gamma(t))} & 0 \end{bmatrix} T(t). \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Then,

$$D^{\gamma(t)} T(t) = t^{1-\gamma(t)} \theta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} T(t), \tag{11}$$

where

$$\theta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))} & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\gamma(t))} & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Now, by using operational matrix of variable order fractional derivative of Taylor polynomials, we obtain operational matrix of variable order fractional derivative of Bessel polynomials as

$$\begin{aligned}
 D^{\gamma(t)} J(t) &= D^{\gamma(t)}(PT(t)) = PD^{\gamma(t)}(T(t)) \\
 &= t^{1-\gamma(t)} P\theta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} P^{-1} J(t).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{12}$$

Consequently, we get

$$D^{\gamma(t)} J(t) = t^{1-\gamma(t)} \eta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} J(t), \quad \eta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} = P\theta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} P^{-1},
 \tag{13}$$

where $\eta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)}$ is called operational matrix of variable order fractional derivative of Bessel polynomials for $0 < \gamma(t) \leq 1$. Also, can be calculated the operational matrix of variable order fractional derivative of Bessel polynomials for $1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2$:

$$D^{\gamma(t)} J(t) = t^{2-\gamma(t)} \eta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)} J(t), \quad \eta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)} = P\theta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)} P^{-1},
 \tag{14}$$

where

$$\theta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Gamma(4)}{\Gamma(4-\gamma(t))} & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\gamma(t))} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\eta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)}$ is called operational matrix of variable order fractional derivative of Bessel polynomials for $1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2$. The matrix form of variable order fractional derivative of $J(t)^2$ is obtained by using Taylor polynomials as

$$\begin{aligned}
 D^{\gamma(t)}(T(t)^2) &= D^{\gamma(t)} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & t & \cdots & t^N \\ t & t^2 & \cdots & t^{N+1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ t^N & t^{N+1} & \cdots & t^{2N} \end{bmatrix} \right) \\
 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))} t^{1-\gamma(t)} & \cdots & \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\gamma(t))} t^{N-\gamma(t)} \\ \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))} t^{1-\gamma(t)} & \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} t^{2-\gamma(t)} & \cdots & \frac{\Gamma(N+2)}{\Gamma(N+2-\gamma(t))} t^{N+1-\gamma(t)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\gamma(t))} t^{N-\gamma(t)} & \frac{\Gamma(N+2)}{\Gamma(N+2-\gamma(t))} t^{N+1-\gamma(t)} & \cdots & \frac{\Gamma(2N+1)}{\Gamma(2N+1-\gamma(t))} t^{2N-\gamma(t)} \end{bmatrix} \\
 &= M_{\gamma(t)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

As a result, by using of Eq. (5) and above matrix, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 D^{\gamma(t)}(J(t)^2) &= D^{\gamma(t)}(PT(t)T^T(t)P^T) \\
 &= PD^{\gamma(t)}(T(t)T^T(t))P^T = PM_{\gamma(t)}P^T.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

5 Method of solution

In this section, we use collocation method to solve variable order fractional problems as

- Variable-order fractional differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}_0D_t^{\gamma_1(t)} u(t) &= f(t, u(t), {}_0D_t^{\gamma_2(t)} u(t), u'(t), u''(t)), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \gamma_1(t), \gamma_2(t) \leq 2, \\
 u(0) &= \mu_1, \quad u'(0) = \mu_2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{16}$$

- Variable-order fractional functional boundary value problems:

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}u(t) &= f(t, u(t), u(\tau(t)), u'(t)), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \gamma(t) \leq 2, \\
 u(0) &= \mu_1, \quad u(1) = \mu_2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{17}$$

- Variable-order fractional pantograph differential equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}u(t) &= f(t, u(\alpha_1t), u(\alpha_2t), \dots, u(\alpha_l t)), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \gamma(t) \leq 2, \quad 0 < \alpha_i \leq 1, \\
 u(0) &= \mu_1, \quad u'(0) = \mu_2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{18}$$

To solve above problems, the unknown function $u(t)$ can be expanded as

$$u(t) \simeq A^T J(t), \tag{19}$$

where

$$A = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_N]^T,$$

using Eqs. (9) and (19) , we get:

$$D^m u(t) \simeq D^m(A^T J(t)) = A^T D^m(J(t)) = A^T Q_m J(t), \quad m \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{20}$$

From Eqs. (13), (14), (19) and the property of Caputo variable-order fractional derivative in Definition 1, we expansion the function ${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}u(t)$ for $0 < \gamma(t) \leq 1$,

$${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}u(t) \simeq D^{\gamma(t)}(A^T J(t)) = A^T D^{\gamma(t)}(J(t)) = t^{1-\gamma(t)} A^T \eta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} J(t), \tag{21}$$

for $1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2$, we get

$${}_0D_t^{\gamma(t)}u(t) = t^{2-\gamma(t)} A^T \eta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)} J(t). \tag{22}$$

Also, we expansion the function $u(\tau(t))$, by using Eq. (19) as

$$u(\tau(t)) \simeq A^T J(\tau(t)), \tag{23}$$

in particular,

$$u(\alpha_i t) \simeq A^T J(\alpha_i t), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, l. \tag{24}$$

Substituting Eqs. (19)-(24) in Eqs. (16)-(18), we get an algebraic equation with $N + 1$ unknown Bessel coefficients for each of Eqs. (16)-(18). Then, we collocate this system at the following points

$$t_i = \frac{2i - 1}{N}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N + 1 - j, \tag{25}$$

so that, $j = 1$ for a initial condition and $j = 2$ for two initial conditions. These equations give $N - 1$ or $N - 2$ non-linear algebraic equations. Now, we approximate initial conditions by Bessel polynomials for different case of fractional differential equations as

$$A^T J(0) = \mu_1, \quad A^T Q_1 J(0) = \mu_2, \tag{26}$$

or

$$A^T J(0) = \mu_1, \quad A^T J(1) = \mu_2. \tag{27}$$

With regards to non-linear algebraic equations and initial conditions, we have a system of algebraic equations with $N + 1$ unknown Bessel coefficients. Consequently, which can be solved last system of non-linear algebraic equations, for the unknown vector A , by using Newton's iterative method.

6 Error analysis

In this section, we investigate the convergence analysis of our proposed method. Let u be a function and a some point from the interior of its domain. Assume that u has derivatives of all orders at a . Then, we define its Taylor series at a by the formula

$$u(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{u^{(n)}(t)}{n!} (t - a)^n,$$

this statement holds for any constant coefficients $0 < \lambda \leq 1$, as

$$u(\lambda t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{u^{(n)}(t)}{n!} (\lambda t - a)^n. \tag{28}$$

Therefore, we can write

$$u(\lambda t) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{u^{(n)}(t)}{n!} (\lambda t - a)^n + R_N(\lambda t), \tag{29}$$

so that,

$$|R_N(\lambda t)| \leq \frac{M_N}{(N + 1)!} (\lambda t - a)^{N+1}, \quad \sup_{t \in [0,1]} |u^{(N+1)}(t)| = M_N. \tag{30}$$

Theorem 6.1. *Suppose $u(\lambda t) \in C^{N+1}[0, \frac{1}{\lambda}]$, $0 < \lambda \leq 1$ and $u_N(\lambda t) = A^T J(\lambda t)$ be the approximate solution obtained by the present method in previous section. If $\tilde{u}_N(\lambda t) = \tilde{A}^T \tilde{J}(\lambda t)$ be the Bessel polynomials of first kind expansion of the exact solution $u(\lambda t)$, where*

$$\tilde{J}(\lambda t) = [\tilde{J}_0(\lambda t), \tilde{J}_1(\lambda t), \dots, \tilde{J}_N(\lambda t)]^T, \quad \tilde{A} = [\tilde{a}_0, \tilde{a}_1, \dots, \tilde{a}_N]^T,$$

and

$$\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!(k+n)!} \left(\frac{\lambda t}{2}\right)^{2k+n}, \quad 0 \leq t < \infty,$$

where the set of Bessel polynomials of first kind $\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t)$ in $L^2[0, 1]$ is orthogonal with respect to the weight function $w(t) = t$,

$$\int_0^1 w(t) [\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t)]^2 dt = \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(\lambda)]^2.$$

Then obtain the upper bound of the error, as

$$\|u(\lambda t) - u_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} \leq \frac{M_N \lambda^{N+1}}{(N + 1)! \sqrt{2N + 4}} + \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \theta_N + \|A\|_2 \omega_N, \tag{31}$$

where

$$\theta_N = \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(\lambda)]^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \omega_N = \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{4k+2n}}{(k!(k+n)! 2^{2k+n})^2 (4k + 2n + 2)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Proof. we can write

$$\|u(\lambda t) - u_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} \leq \|u(\lambda t) - \tilde{u}_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} + \|\tilde{u}_N(\lambda t) - u_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2}, \tag{32}$$

from Eq. (28), we define

$$p_N(\lambda t) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{f^{(n)}(t)}{n!} (\lambda t)^n,$$

since $\tilde{u}_N(\lambda t)$ is the best approximation of $u(\lambda t)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|u(\lambda t) - \tilde{u}_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} &= \left(\int_0^1 |u(\lambda t) - \tilde{A}^T \tilde{J}(\lambda t)|^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \left(\int_0^1 |u(\lambda t) - p_N(\lambda t)|^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{M_N^2}{((N+1)!)^2} \int_0^1 (\lambda t)^{2N+2} t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \frac{M_N \lambda^{N+1}}{(N+1)! \sqrt{2N+4}}. \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Also, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{u}_N(\lambda t) - u_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} &= \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N \tilde{a}_n \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - \sum_{n=0}^N a_n J_n(\lambda t) \right\|_{L_w^2} \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N \tilde{a}_n \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - \sum_{n=0}^N a_n \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) \right\|_{L_w^2} + \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N a_n \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - \sum_{n=0}^N a_n J_n(\lambda t) \right\|_{L_w^2} \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N (\tilde{a}_n - a_n) \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) \right\|_{L_w^2} + \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N a_n (\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - J_n(\lambda t)) \right\|_{L_w^2} \\ &= \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N (\tilde{a}_n - a_n) \tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) \right]^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N a_n (\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - J_n(\lambda t)) \right]^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |\tilde{a}_n - a_n|^2 \right] \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t)|^2 \right] t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad + \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |a_n|^2 \right] \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - J_n(\lambda t)|^2 \right] t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 t |\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t)|^2 dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 |\tilde{J}_n(\lambda t) - J_n(\lambda t)|^2 t dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

$\|\cdot\|_2$ is 2-norm of vectors. Therefore, by use of orthogonality property of Bessel polynomials, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\tilde{u}_N(\lambda t) - u_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(\lambda)]^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &+ \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 \left(\sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k (\lambda t)^{2k+n}}{k!(k+n)!2^{2k+n}} \right)^2 t dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(\lambda)]^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &+ \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{4k+2n} t^{4k+2n+1}}{(k!(k+n)!2^{2k+n})^2} dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(\lambda)]^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &+ \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{4k+2n}}{(k!(k+n)!2^{2k+n})^2 (4k+2n+2)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{35}$$

□

According to Eq. (31)-(35), we determine the upper bound of error for any constant coefficients $0 < \lambda \leq 1$.

In view of the above discussion and Theorem 6.1, we conclude that by increasing the number of the Bessel functions bases, the numerical result convergence to exact solution:

$$N \rightarrow \infty \Rightarrow \|u(\lambda t) - u_N(\lambda t)\|_{L_w^2} \rightarrow 0.$$

7 Illustrative examples

In this section, we test the performance of the scheme on some examples. The computations associated with the examples were performed using MATLAB.

7.1 Differential equation

Example 7.1. Consider the following linear variable-order fractional differential equation [13]

$$\begin{cases} D^{\gamma(t)}u(t) - 10u'(t) + u(t) = g(t), & t \in [0, 1], \\ u(0) = 5, \end{cases}
 \tag{36}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma(t) &= \frac{t + 2 \exp(t)}{7}, \\
 g(t) &= 10 \left(\frac{t^{2-\gamma(t)}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} + \frac{t^{1-\gamma(t)}}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))} \right) + 5t^2 - 90t - 95.
 \end{aligned}$$

The exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = 5(1+t)^2$.

Solution. Applying the proposed method, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} u(t) &\simeq A^T J(t), & u'(t) &\simeq A^T Q_1 J(t), \\ D^{\gamma(t)} u(t) &\simeq t^{1-\gamma(t)} A^T \eta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} J(t). \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Substituting above equations in Eq. (36), we have

$$\begin{aligned} t^{1-\gamma(t)} A^T \eta_{1,N}^{\gamma(t)} J(t) - 10A^T Q_1 J(t) + A^T J(t) &= 10\left(\frac{t^{2-\gamma(t)}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} + \frac{t^{1-\gamma(t)}}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))}\right) \\ &+ 5t^2 - 90t - 95, \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

with initial condition

$$A^T J(0) = 5,$$

Now, we collocate Eq. (38) at the points in Eq. (25), which can be solved for the unknown vector A , using Newton’s iterative method. For $N = 2$, we obtain

$$Q_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.5 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0.5 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\eta_{1,2}^{\frac{t+2exp(t)}{7}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2\Gamma(2-\frac{t+2exp(t)}{7})} & 0 \\ \frac{-1}{\Gamma(3-\frac{t+2exp(t)}{7})} & 0 & \frac{1}{2\Gamma(3-\frac{t+2exp(t)}{7})} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\frac{t+2exp(t)}{7})} & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Replacing Q_1 and $\eta_{1,2}^{\frac{t+2exp(t)}{7}}$ into Eq. (38) with initial condition, we get the following system of algebraic equations

$$\begin{cases} 2.19610618846a_0 - 4.63047433988a_1 - 0.59805309423a_2 + 111.53161056 = 0, \\ 4.31138930829a_0 - 4.11325924065a_1 - 1.65569465414a_2 + 143.49297097 = 0, \\ a_0 - 5.0 = 0. \end{cases}$$

Then, we obtain

$$A = [5, 20, 50]^T,$$

by using Eq. (37), we have

$$u(t) = 5(1 + t)^2,$$

which is the exact solution of Eq. (36). This example was considered in [13] by using Legendre wavelet method for $k = 2, M = 4$, which maximum absolute error for it is 2.0245×10^{-9} .

Example 7.2. Consider the following nonlinear variable-order fractional differential equation [13]

$$\begin{cases} D^{\gamma(t)} u(t) - 7u'(t) + 5u(t) - 6u''(t)u(t) = g(t), & t \in [0, 1], \\ u(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} g(t) &= 5\left(\frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))}t^{2-\gamma(t)} + \frac{3}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))}t^{1-\gamma(t)}\right) - 275t^2 - 895t - 105, \\ \gamma(t) &= \frac{3(\cos(t) + \sin(t))}{5}. \end{aligned}$$

The exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = 5(3t + t^2)$.

Solution. By using the proposed method and considering that $1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2$, we have

$$\begin{cases} t^{2-\gamma(t)}A^T\eta_{2,N}^{\gamma(t)}J(t) - 7A^TQ_1J(t) - 6A^TQ_2J(t)A^TJ(t) = 5\left(\frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))}t^{2-\gamma(t)} + \frac{3}{\Gamma(2-\gamma(t))}t^{1-\gamma(t)}\right) \\ -275t^2 - 895t - 105, \\ A^TJ(0) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Taking $N = 2$, we obtain

$$u(t) = 5(3t + t^2),$$

which is the exact solution. This problem is solved by Legendre wavelet method [13], so that maximum absolute error in it for $k = 2, M = 3$ is 2.2737×10^{-13} . That, the proposed method is more accurate compared to Legendre wavelet method.

Example 7.3. Consider the following nonlinear variable-order fractional differential equation [12]

$$\begin{cases} D^{\frac{\cos(t)}{3}}(u^2(t)) + D^{\frac{t}{2}}u(t) + u'(t) = g(t), & t \in [0, 1], \\ u(0) = 0, \end{cases} \tag{39}$$

with

$$g(t) = 1 + 2t + \frac{4t^{1-\frac{t}{4}}(8 + 7t)}{(-8 + t)(-4 + t)\Gamma(1 - \frac{t}{4})} + \frac{18t^{2-\frac{\cos(t)}{3}}(108(1 + t)^2 - 3(7 + 6t)\cos(t) + \cos^2(t))}{(\cos(t) - 12)(\cos(t) - 9)(\cos(t) - 6)(\cos(t) - 3)\Gamma(1 - \frac{\cos(t)}{3})}.$$

The exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = t + t^2$.

Solution. To solve by using the present method, we have

$$A^T P M_{\frac{\cos(t)}{3}} P^T A + t^{1-\frac{t}{2}} A^T \eta_{1,N}^{\frac{t}{2}} J(t) + A^T Q_1 J(t) = 1 + 2t + \frac{4t^{1-\frac{t}{4}}(8 + 7t)}{(-8 + t)(-4 + t)\Gamma(1 - \frac{t}{4})} + \frac{18t^{2-\frac{\cos(t)}{3}}(108(1 + t)^2 - 3(7 + 6t)\cos(t) + \cos^2(t))}{(\cos(t) - 12)(\cos(t) - 9)(\cos(t) - 6)(\cos(t) - 3)\Gamma(1 - \frac{\cos(t)}{3})},$$

with initial condition

$$A^T J(0) = 0,$$

and taking $N = 2$, we have

$$A = [-5.95009 \times 10^{-31}, 2, 8]^T,$$

as a result,

$$u(t) = t + t^2 - 5.95009 \times 10^{-31}.$$

The approximate solution of Eq. (39) obtained by Bernstein polynomials for $n = 2, 3, 4$ plotted in [11]. Due to the those figures in [12], we can conclude that the result obtained by the present method more accurate compared to Bernstein polynomials.

Example 7.4. Consider the following nonlinear variable-order fractional differential equation [12]

$$\begin{cases} D^{\frac{e^t}{3}}(u^2(t)) + D^{\frac{t}{2}}u(t) + u'(t) = g(t), & t \in [0, 1] \\ u(0) = 0 \end{cases}$$

with

$$g(t) = 3t^2 + \frac{720t^{6-\frac{e^t}{3}}}{\Gamma(7 - \frac{e^t}{3})} - \frac{48t^{3-\frac{t}{2}}}{(t - 6)(t - 4)(t - 2)\Gamma(1 - \frac{t}{2})}.$$

The exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = t^3$.

Solution. Applying the proposed method with $N = 3$, we obtain

$$u(t) = t^3 - 2.3652 \times 10^{-17}t^2 + 1.8037 \times 10^{-30}t.$$

This example was considered in [12] by using Bernstein polynomials for $N = 3$, we can conclude that the result obtained by the present method more accurate compared to Bernstein polynomials.

7.2 Functional boundary value problem

Example 7.5. Consider the following variable-order fractional functional boundary value problem [4, 18]

$$\begin{cases} D^{\gamma(t)}u(t) + \cos(t)u'(t) + 4u(t) + 5u(t^2) = g(t), & t \in [0, 1], \\ u(0) = 0, & u(1) = 1 \end{cases}$$

with

$$g(t) = \frac{2t^{2-\gamma(t)}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} + 5t^4 + 4t^2 + 2t \cos(t),$$

and

$$\gamma(t) = \frac{5 + \sin(t)}{4}.$$

The exact solution is $u(t) = t^2$.

Solution. By applying the method described in Section 5, the exact solution for $N = 2$ is obtained. Due to the absolute errors table in [4], [18], present method more accurate compared with those methods. Respectively, maximum absolute error for $M = 12$ is 1.11×10^{-16} and maximum absolute error for kernel method with $n = 40$ is 3.87×10^{-8} .

Example 7.6. Consider the following variable-order fractional functional boundary value problem [4, 18]

$$\begin{cases} D^{\gamma(t)}u(t) + e^t u'(t) + 2u(t) + 8u(e^{t-1}) = g(t), & t \in [0, 1], \quad 1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2, \\ u(0) = 4, & u(1) = 9, \end{cases}$$

with

$$g(t) = \frac{2t^{2-\gamma(t)}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma(t))} + 2(t^2 + 4t + 4) + 8(4e^{t-1} + e^{2t-2} + 4) + e^t(2t + 4),$$

and the exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = t^2 + 4t + 4$. we solved this problem by taking $\gamma(t) = \frac{6+\cos(t)}{4}$ and $\gamma(t) = \frac{20-\exp(t)}{10}$.

Solution. By applying the method described in Section 5, the exact solution for $N = 2$ is obtained. Also, with regards to absolute errors table in [4], [18], we can conclude that the result obtained by the present method more accurate compared to those methods.

7.3 Pantograph differential equation

Example 7.7. Consider the following variable-order fractional multi-pantograph differential equation with variable coefficients

$$\begin{cases} D^{\gamma(t)}u(t) = -u(t) + t^2u(\frac{t}{2}) + tu(\frac{t}{4}) + g(t), & t \in [0, 1], \quad 0 < \gamma(t) \leq 1, \\ u(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

with

$$g(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\gamma(t))} \int_0^t (t-x)^{-\gamma(t)} (3x^2e^{-x} - x^3e^{-x}) dx + t^3e^{-t} - \frac{t^5}{8}e^{-\frac{t}{2}} - \frac{t^4}{64}e^{-\frac{t}{4}},$$

and the exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = t^3e^{-t}$.

Table 1: Absolute errors with various values of N for Example 7.7.

x	$\gamma(t) = \cos(t)$			$\gamma(t) = \frac{t+2\exp(t)}{7}$		
	$N = 3$	$N = 5$	$N = 7$	$N = 3$	$N = 5$	$N = 7$
0	0	2.26×10^{-30}	2.59×10^{-29}	3.69×10^{-31}	3.46×10^{-30}	6.47×10^{-29}
0.1	3.47×10^{-3}	1.35×10^{-4}	8.60×10^{-7}	1.58×10^{-3}	1.07×10^{-5}	3.29×10^{-8}
0.2	4.75×10^{-3}	9.06×10^{-5}	5.71×10^{-7}	1.11×10^{-4}	2.37×10^{-5}	5.58×10^{-8}
0.3	3.26×10^{-3}	6.76×10^{-5}	5.71×10^{-7}	1.60×10^{-3}	1.02×10^{-5}	2.57×10^{-8}
0.4	2.06×10^{-3}	7.75×10^{-5}	5.28×10^{-7}	2.16×10^{-3}	1.50×10^{-5}	6.74×10^{-8}
0.5	1.88×10^{-3}	8.32×10^{-5}	4.64×10^{-7}	1.26×10^{-3}	1.04×10^{-5}	1.52×10^{-7}
0.6	2.65×10^{-3}	7.14×10^{-5}	4.68×10^{-7}	6.53×10^{-4}	1.85×10^{-5}	2.11×10^{-7}
0.7	3.79×10^{-3}	6.65×10^{-5}	4.38×10^{-7}	2.58×10^{-3}	2.43×10^{-5}	4.75×10^{-7}
0.8	4.34×10^{-3}	9.52×10^{-5}	4.49×10^{-7}	3.15×10^{-3}	2.80×10^{-5}	8.08×10^{-7}
0.9	3.10×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-4}	7.58×10^{-7}	7.89×10^{-4}	6.73×10^{-5}	7.97×10^{-7}
1.0	1.21×10^{-3}	1.09×10^{-4}	8.56×10^{-7}	6.21×10^{-3}	2.11×10^{-4}	3.31×10^{-6}

Figure 1: Absolute error between the exact and approximate solution with various functions of $\gamma(t)$ and $N = 5$ for Example 7.7.

Solution. The absolute errors between the exact solution and approximate solution for different functions of $\gamma(t) = \cos(t)$ and $\gamma(t) = \frac{t+2\exp(t)}{7}$ with various values of N , can be seen from Table 1. The absolute error between exact and approximate solution with various functions of $\gamma(t)$ for $N = 5$ is plot in Figure 1.

Example 7.8. Consider the following variable-order fractional nonlinear pantograph differential equation

$$\begin{cases} D^{\gamma(t)}u(t) = 1 - 2u^2(\frac{t}{2}), & t \in [0, 1], \quad 1 < \gamma(t) \leq 2. \\ u(0) = 1, \quad u'(0) = 0. \end{cases}$$

The exact solution of this problem, when $\gamma = 2$ is $u(t) = \cos(t)$.

Solution. Table 2, displays the absolute errors between the exact and approximate solutions for $\gamma(t) = 2$ with various values of N . Also, we presented numerical solutions for various functions of $\gamma(t)$ with various values of $N = 5$ in Figure 2 and 3. With regards to these figure and table, it is seen that the approximate solutions converge to the exact solution.

8 Conclusion

In the present work, we solved wide class of the variable-order fractional problems by using Bessel collocation method and their operational matrices of integer and variable order fractional derivative. The main

Table 2: Absolute errors with various values of N with $\gamma(t) = 2$ for Example 7.8.

t	Present method			Method in [23]
	$N = 3$	$N = 5$	$N = 7$	$k = 2, M = 5$
0	0	0	0	2.33×10^{-7}
0.2	4.42×10^{-4}	2.60×10^{-6}	2.16×10^{-8}	8.01×10^{-8}
0.4	7.99×10^{-4}	4.29×10^{-6}	7.01×10^{-8}	3.78×10^{-8}
0.6	7.74×10^{-4}	6.09×10^{-6}	1.43×10^{-7}	1.01×10^{-4}
0.8	1.53×10^{-3}	6.64×10^{-6}	2.37×10^{-7}	1.42×10^{-4}
1.0	5.56×10^{-3}	3.03×10^{-5}	4.12×10^{-7}	–

Figure 2: Approximate solution for various values of $\gamma(t)$ with $N = 5$ of Example 7.8.

Figure 3: Approximate solution for various functions of $\gamma(t)$ with $N = 5$ of Example 7.8.

advantage of the proposed scheme is using few terms of Bessel polynomials to obtain approximate solutions. Also, reasonable upper bound of error for approximate solution of any functions are presented, which was proved that the method is convergent. Moreover, we have solved lots of examples in various fields, which considered a limited number of them, indicating that this method is more accurate than other methods.

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Email: h.dehestani@alzahra.ac.ir

Email: ordokhani@alzahra.ac.ir